

On the Irrationality of Certain Constants Related to the Smarandache Function

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1. Let $S(n)$ be the Smarandache function. Recently I. Cojocaru and S. Cojocaru [2] have proved the irrationality of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{S(n)}{n!}$.

The author of this note [5] showed that this is a consequence of an old irrationality criteria (which will be used here once again), and proved a result implying the irrationality of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \frac{S(n)}{n!}$.

E. Burton [1] has studied series of type $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!}$, which has a value $\in \left(e - \frac{5}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right)$. He showed that the series $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+r)!}$ is convergent for all $r \in \mathbf{N}$. I. Cojocaru and S. Cojocaru [3] have introduced the "third constant of Smarandache" namely $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(2)S(3)\dots S(n)}$, which has a value between $\frac{71}{100}$ and $\frac{97}{100}$. Our aim in the following is to prove that the constants introduced by Burton and Cojocaru-Cojocaru are all irrational.

2. The first result is in fact a refinement of an old irrationality criteria (see [4] p.5):

Theorem 1. *Let (x_n) be a sequence of nonnegative integers having the properties:*

- (1) *there exists $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}^*$ such that $x_n \leq n$ for all $n \geq n_0$;*
- (2) *$x_n < n - 1$ for infinitely many n ;*
- (3) *$x_m > 0$ for an infinity of m .*

Then the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x_n}{n!}$ is irrational.

Let now $x_n = S(n - 1)$. Then

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!} = \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \frac{x_n}{n!}.$$

Here $S(n - 1) \leq n - 1 < n$ for all $n \geq 2$; $S(m - 1) < m - 2$ for $m > 3$ composite, since by $S(m - 1) < \frac{2}{3}(m - 1) < m - 2$ for $m > 4$ this holds true. (For the inequality $S(k) < \frac{2}{3}k$ for $k > 3$ composite, see [6]). Finally, $S(m - 1) > 0$ for all $m \geq 1$. This proves the irrationality of $\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+1)!}$.

Analogously, write

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{S(k)}{(k+r)!} = \sum_{m=r+2}^{\infty} \frac{S(m-r)}{m!}.$$

Put $x_m = S(m - r)$. Here $S(m - r) \leq m - r < m$, $S(m - r) \leq m - r < m - 1$ for $r \geq 2$, and $S(m - r) > 0$ for $m \geq r + 2$. Thus, the above series is irrational for $r \geq 2$, too.

3. The third constant of Smarandache will be studied with the following irrationality criterion (see [4], p.8):

Theorem 2. Let $(a_n), (b_n)$ be two sequences of nonnegative integers satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $a_n > 0$ for an infinity of n ;
- (2) $b_n \geq 2$, $0 \leq a_n \leq b_n - 1$ for all $n \geq 1$;
- (3) there exists an increasing sequence (i_n) of positive integers such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_{i_n} = +\infty, \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_{i_n}/b_{i_n} = 0.$$

Then the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n}$ is irrational.

Corollary. For $b_n \geq 2$, (b_n) positive integers, (b_n) unbounded the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b_1 b_2 \dots b_n}$ is irrational.

Proof. Let $a_n \equiv 1$. Since $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n = +\infty$, there exists a sequence (i_n) such that $b_{i_n} \rightarrow \infty$. Then $\frac{1}{b_{i_n}} \rightarrow 0$, and the three conditions of Theorem 2 are verified.

By selecting $b_n \equiv S(n)$, we have $b_p = S(p) = p \rightarrow \infty$ for p a prime, so by the above Corollary, the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S(1)S(2)\dots S(n)}$ is irrational.

References

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- [4] J. Sándor, *Irrational Numbers* (Romanian), Univ. Timișoara, Caiete Metodico-Stiințifice No.44, 1987, pp. 1-18.
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